

The WIDER UPTAKE roadmap guide – 1st version

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ABSTRACT

Deliverable 6.6 (D6.6) is the first version of the WIDER UPTAKE roadmap guide, a manual to organise transition planning for wider uptake of water-smart solutions and the uptake of symbiotic circular economy solutions (SCES). It follows D6.3 as the second deliverable from Task 6.1 “Roadmap for wider uptake of water-smart solutions.”

The roadmap structure is divided into four main steps: scoping, forecasting, backcasting, and transfer. The four main steps are structured into different numbers of working steps. Each road mapping step and working step is enriched with detailed explanations and references to supporting templates pointing at tools developed, or under development, in other work packages (WP) of WIDER UPTAKE. The D6.6 maps the outcomes from other WPs that support the creation of a roadmap, and that will be fully embedded as a customized supporting tool in the final version of the guide, D6.7.

D6.6 and the following enhanced version D6.7 (due at the month 48 of the WIDER UPTAKE project) are designed as a manual to organise transition planning for wider uptake of water-smart solutions and the uptake of symbiotic circular economy solutions (SCES).

KEYWORDS

Water smart solutions, roadmap, circular economy.

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1 Executive summary

WP6 aims to develop a roadmap for wider uptake of water-smart solutions that can guide the users to achieve a water-smart society through the realization of symbiotic circular economy solutions (SCES). The roadmap guide is addressed to managers and decision makers providing water services and related solutions in the water sector. This document is the second in a series of deliverables to develop the roadmap. It follows deliverable 6.3 (D6.3), which provided a clear definition of the roadmap steps, the preliminary version of data to be gathered at each step and the description of the WIDER UPTAKE case studies in terms of drivers, barriers, and pressures to the uptake of SCES. Building on the information provided in D6.3, this deliverable, D6.6, is the first version of the roadmap guide: it further elaborates on the general road mapping approach developed in the TRUST project and points at supporting template to perform a road mapping exercise with reference to outcomes from other WIDER UPTAKE WPs where relevant. The advancement of the state of the art with respect to TRUST has been the adaptation of the approach to the domain of WIDER UPTAKE and the proposed integration to be completed in D6.7 with specific assessment tools developed in this project.

A final version of the roadmap guide will be prepared (D6.7, due in month M48, i.e., April 2024) with customization and refinement of the templates based on the results of the relevant WPs involved. D6.7 will also account for lessons learnt after testing the roadmap guide in selected cases to validate the approach and be informed by the synthesis chapters across the case studies provided in D6.3 and the following D6.4 (due in month M42).

2 Introduction

Water-smart solutions are thought to involve industrial symbiosis and support the transition to a water-smart society by increased resource efficiency, limiting emissions, and facilitating development a circular economy in the water sector. Despite the urgent need, implementation of water-smart solutions is limited, and the barriers are not only technological but also of organizational, regulatory, social, and economic character.

The overall objective of WIDER UPTAKE is to facilitate industrial symbiosis by co-development of a roadmap towards wider uptake of water-smart solutions for wastewater reuse and resource recovery. This will be based on the principles of circular economy (CE).

A roadmap enables decision makers to plan and implement a pathway to achieve desired objectives through a road mapping process. WP6 aims to develop a roadmap for wider uptake of water-smart solutions through the realization of symbiotic circular economy solutions (SCES). This document, D6.6, is the second in a series of deliverables to develop the roadmap (see Figure 1 and Table 1 below).

According to the vision proposed by Water Europe in 2017, a water-smart society is as follows: *“a society in which the true value of water is recognized and realized, and all available water sources are managed in such a way that water scarcity and the pollution of groundwater are avoided. Water and resource loops are largely closed to foster a circular economy and optimal resource efficiency, while the water system is resilient against the impact of climate change events”* (Water Europe, 2017).

WIDER UPTAKE embraces this definition as the vision guiding the creation of roadmaps in WP6.

A revised version of Water Europe’s definition of water-smart society was recently published (Water Europe, 2023). The new version is slightly extended with objectives and emphasises the importance of people, both with respect to demographic change and stakeholder engagement. However, the revision does not change the overall message or the background for the work presented in this deliverable.

The approach of the roadmap guide is grounded on the one proposed by the TRUST project by Hein *et al.* (2010) and adapted to the scope and domain of WIDER UPTAKE. Starting from the general aspects described in D6.3 (Akon-Yamga et al, 2023), each road mapping step is enriched here, in D6.6, with further explanations and pointing at material and tools developed, or under development, in other WPs of WIDER UPTAKE, proposed as supporting templates when developing a roadmap. D6.6 maps the roadmap working steps versus the outcomes of WIDER UPTAKE that can support the guide users in creating their roadmap. Those outcomes will be tailored and customized as supporting templates in the final version of the guide, D6.7.

The roadmap guide is addressed to managers and decision makers providing water services and related solutions in the water sector.

The roadmap will help find the individual pathway to the uptake of SCES, focusing on individual/regional/local adaptation needs and the ambitions of the cities/regions.

The roadmapping starts with the SCES of interest and guides the roadmap team through a sequence of working steps to come up with an action plan (the roadmap) that helps to assess the compliance of the SCES in achieving set objectives and to define what should be done to realize it; the process might also lead to the identification of alternative SCES that are more sustainable and water-smart based on a collaborative dialogue and comprehensive analysis promoted by the roadmapping process.

As in TRUST (Hein *et al.* (2010)), the WIDER UPTAKE roadmap procedure is structured in four main stages: Scoping (S), Forecasting (F), Backcasting (B) and Transfer (TR). Each stage has a different number of working steps designed to help organise the communication and iterative work of collecting information and defining measures to adapt towards identified future needs and the desired elements of a sustainable future wider uptake.

Although the process and related working steps are the same as those proposed in TRUST, the advancement beyond the state of the art here has been adopting and adapting the approach to the domain of WIDER UPTAKE and the proposed integration with specific assessment tools developed in this project. In D6.6, the integration is mainly presented as a reference to the identified products. The final supporting templates will be integrated into D6.7, envisaged as an interactive guide embedding hyperlinks to the relevant tools.

Furthermore, the roadmap approach proposed in this deliverable will be validated by selected case studies of the project to comment on the practicability and feasibility of the concept. It will give feedback to the authors of this guideline and supporting templates as inputs to the final version D6.7.

D6.7 will include further information specific to the context of developing water-smart and sustainable SCES, i.e., objectives, drivers, pressures, trends, and future scenarios based on the discussion in D6.3 and D6.4 and be further informed by the input from the final tasks of WP2, WP3, WP4 and WP5.

The discussion in D6.3 specified the potential/generalised solutions, drivers, pressures, and trends related to achieving a water-smart society's objectives by synthesising the examples collected from the demonstration cases and specifying the preliminary database structure required for the data.

In D6.4, common features in the scenarios used for the testing of the methods and tools developed in WP2, WP3, WP4 and WP5 will be identified to provide a set of future scenarios and guidance on how to define scenarios that will be included for further use in the roadmap guide.

Finally, an analysis of results/experiences/insights gained through the activities in WIDER UPTAKE, including the application of the roadmap guide on selected demonstration cases,

should be prepared as a report (D6.8, due in month 48) presenting a strategic level discussion and concluding with recommendations for achieving wider uptake of water-smart solutions.

Figure 1: Sequence and timeline of roadmap deliverables

Table 1: Sequence and timeline of roadmap deliverables

Deliverable number	Deliverable title	Due month in the project lifetime
D6.3	Roadmap database	34
D6.4	Report from scenario analysis	42
D6.6	The WIDER UPTAKE roadmap guide – 1 st version	36
D6.7	The WIDER UPTAKE roadmap guide (final version)	48
D6.8	Results of the roadmap applications	48

It is worth explaining that within the project, the SCES have already been selected. Therefore, each case study has already performed a decision process to arrive at the solutions that are to be, or have been, implemented. In the latter case, action plans for their realization have already been made before the project started. Gathering the information about those decision processes will inform this guide in the following version, so to ground the general approach proposed by TRUST on the real cases experience and become a valuable tool to be adopted by any interested user also, and mostly, outside the project. Through this, the road mapping guide is co-created with demonstration case stakeholders and other relevant WPs in WIDER UPTAKE, but it is not strictly implemented during the project lifetime.

For the implementation outside of WIDER UPTAKE, the time scale of the roadmap procedure should cover a duration of one or two years (a timeline of 18 months is proposed in Chapter 3), to accommodate the fact that the roadmap core team and the participating institutions and stakeholders have to launch a continuous, common process and a mutual understanding for the roadmap exercise.

Regarding the structure of D6.6, after the executive summary and this introduction, the following chapters are provided to the reader:

- Chapter 3 provides instructions on how to organize the process of road mapping, on the roles of involved participants and a suggestion for the possible timeline for the exercise.
- Chapter 4 is the actual preliminary version of the WIDER UPTAKE roadmap guide and describes important general aspects to organise the roadmap exercise.
- Chapter 5 closes the deliverable with final remarks and information related to the further steps towards the final version of the roadmap guide.

3 HOW TO ORGANISE THE ROADMAP WORK

3.1 Organizing the road mapping exercise

The roadmap procedure should be organised by a roadmap core team. The core team should be led and organised by a responsible person known as the “roadmap manager”. The roadmap manager and the core team will organise data collection, sum up the results of data collection and input information, provide interpretation of data and organise workshops with the actors involved. The roadmap core team and the actors comprise the roadmap working group.

The relevant people from the actors and governance systems should participate actively in the working group and will support the work of the roadmap core team. The working group is proposed to be organized as a Local Community of Practice (CoP). As described in D7.6 (Damman and Lund, 2021), a community of practice is an approach to establish and facilitate social learning and co-development towards a common objective. The overall objective in WIDER UPTAKE is related to upscaling of water smart solutions. The Local CoPs in WIDER UPTAKE are established to promote innovation uptake and realise more specific aims related to industrial symbiosis (IS) based on circular economy solutions in the water sector.

In line with the approach proposed for the management of Local CoPs (D7.6), which requires a CoP manager and a CoP core group, the composition of the road map team follows the same categories of roles.

The creation of the roadmap can be seen as an exercise to be performed by an established Local CoP, where the CoP manager takes the role of roadmap manager, the CoP core team is the roadmap core team, and the working group is the local CoP itself.

3.2 Expected duration of the road mapping exercise

The duration of the road mapping exercise depends on the content, engagement of participants, challenges to be addressed and availability of information. However, as a realistic target for initiating, launching, working, and collecting the roadmap exercise, a total duration of 18 months should be considered, according to the experience gained in projects such as TRUST; however, the shorter, the better since decision makers need results on a short time scale.

In WIDER UPTAKE, the 18 months duration and GANTT chart proposed in TRUST is adopted. The users can adapt the time scale based on their specific challenges and context.

Figure 2: Suggested Timeline for the roadmap exercise (based on Hein et al. (2010))

3.3 Organization

The WIDER UPTAKE road mapping process involved a four-step approach, as outlined in detail in Chapter 4. All steps are connected, but each has a distinct method, materials, and outcomes. The roadmap approach is grounded on the outcome of workshops organized by the roadmap core team with the actors involved in the working group. The workshops are cooperative process to engage the key actors and stakeholders in co-creating a clear and well-designed implementation plan. The work might require internal meetings and adjustments by the core team. Those adjustments are not included in the timeline of the roadmap process and should be organized on the need by the core team.

To perform a roadmap exercise, besides dedicated workshops, data should be available and organized to serve as inputs to the different steps of a roadmap creation or depicted results of each step.

4 The WIDER UPTAKE ROADMAP GUIDE

The road mapping exercise is the result of the iterative four stage process, consisting of the following steps: scoping, forecasting, backcasting and transfer. The four main stages are structured into different numbers of working steps as illustrated in Figure 3. Each working step is described in the following chapters by reflecting similar key aspects in the form of a summarizing table presenting: what is the target of the step? What methods are used in the step? Who will participate in addressing the step? What data is relevant for the step? Where will be the output from the step used as input in other steps of the roadmap? What is the suggested start – and endpoint? Furthermore, for each step, the table provides the example of proposed templates to be used. Note that most of the templates will be customized for D6.7 when most of the outcomes of the project will be available and the guide will be validated by the interaction with selected case studies. In D6.6 the templates to be extracted from identified deliverables of other WPs and adapted in D6.7 are indicated in *Italics* under each working step.

Figure 3: Schematic diagram of the roadmap process.

The WIDER UPTAKE road mapping exercise will take advantages of the interactions with the outcomes derived from WP2-5 and the demonstrations of the water-smart symbiotic solutions in WP1. This version of the guide, D6.6, maps and refers to the relevant outcomes from the project (already available or under development) that will be made available to the users of the guide in the last version, D6.7. Currently, mainly outcomes from WP4, 5 and 7 have been referred to, but the list might be extended after a phase of validation with the selected case study owners and WP leaders, along with the availability of the final outcomes from other WP6 and other WPs (Figure 4).

<p>Scoping:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • S1: Identifying relevant actors • S2: Objectives of the SCES • S3: Elements of the SCES • S4: Drivers, pressures, and trends towards a water-smart society 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To S1: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assessment chart – Context description (in chapter 5.1, D4.1 - Damman et al., 2021) (WP4) • Actor management document (new) • To S2: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SCES map (new) • Semi-structured interviews, D4.1, ANNEX 2 (Damman et al., 2021) (WP4) • Assessment charts and excel file of GOCIWA tool, section 5.2, 5.3, 5.4 and Annex 3 of D4.1 (Damman et al., 2021) (WP4) • List of objectives and criteria based on D5.1, chapter 6 (Nessler Seglem K and Helness, 2023) (WP5) • To S3: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • water-smartness assessment framework, based on D5.1 (Nessler Seglem K and Helness, 2023) (WP5) • Confidentiality Agreement and Code of Conduct (new) • Context information (new) • To S4: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Water-smartness assessment framework, based on D5.1 (Nessler Seglem K and Helness, 2023) (WP5) • Driver, Pressure and Trends overview resulting from S4 (based on D6.3, to be revised in D6.7) (WP6)
<p>Forecasting :</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • F1: Projecting possible futures (or scenarios) • F2: Envisioning the system in the future • F3: Synthesising 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To F1: Examples of factors to be assessed in projecting different futures (copied from the GOCIWA tool, D4.1 (Damman et al., 2021) (WP4) to be customized or adapted and included in D6.7 based on D6.4 • To F2: water-smartness assessment framework, based on D5.1 (Nessler Seglem K and Helness, 2023) (WP5)
<p>Backcasting:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • B1: defining intermediate states • B2: Identifying transition measures 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To B1: Water-smartness assessment framework, based on D5.1 (Nessler Seglem K and Helness, 2023) (WP5) • To B2: Water-smartness assessment framework, based on D5.1 (Nessler Seglem K and Helness, 2023) (WP5)
<p>Transfer:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • TR1: Evaluating transfer action fields and their measures • TR2: Creating the roadmap 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To T1: Prioritized action plan (new) • To T2: Roadmap template (new)

Figure 4: Overview of the outcomes of WIDER UPTAKE WPs to be customized and embedded into the final version of the guide, as for D6.6.

Indeed, WIDER UPTAKE provides different instruments to assess transition needs and processes useful at different steps of the roadmap creation. A governance assessment tool (GOCIWA) (WP4), a method for determining health and quality risks (WP2), methodologies for assessing circularity and resource efficiency (WP3), business models and transition pathways (WP4), and a framework for assessing water smartness and sustainability (WS&S assessment framework) (WP5) have been developed or are under development at the time of writing. These are tools and methodologies that provide valuable results and insights in their respective domains and may be used alone but have the additional aim of being connected to the roadmap guide, as supporting instruments, either directly or indirectly (e.g., by supporting the assessment of some indicators in the WS&S assessment framework (WP5) when this is used in different working steps of the guide). Furthermore, a database for the project with information from the demonstration cases has been set up in WP2 and it is expected that the database will include functional requirements for supporting the road mapping exercises.

The full overview of the interactions and of the information flow among WPs and from WP1-5 to WP6 is depicted in Figure 5. Figure 5 is a reference map for the developers of the guide in WP6 to visualize the interactions to be established in collaboration with the other WPs in the final version of the guide (D6.7). Those interactions will be created either as additional templates or described in additional sub-sections at the relevant working steps of the guide.

Figure 5: Graphical presentation of the interactions across WPs and information flow feeding the final version of the roadmap guide (D6.7)

4.1 SCOPING: Defining the SCES and boundaries

Scoping is the first main stage of the road mapping exercise and defines the scope of analysis regarding system descriptions and boundaries. It provides a baseline understanding of today’s system and delineates the boundaries. “System” is defined as the SCES and the relevant part of the surrounding environment; further characterization of the SCES will be adopted in the future D6.7.

Figure 6 presents a generic structure of a symbiotic circular economy solution (SCES), which is the term used to describe the types of solutions demonstrated in WIDER UPTAKE. The figure also presents how the boundaries should be drawn.

Figure 6: Illustration of properties of a symbiotic circular economy solution (SCES) and the inputs and impacts on its surroundings (Source: adapted from Nessler Seglem K., Helness H., 2023)

The figure shows that the SCES is not limited to a technological solution. Still, it is realized by the circular process of interactions involving resources, technologies, actors, governance regimes and identified market opportunities that make the implementation of water-smart solutions possible and beneficial.

Gearing and/or modifying one or more of those elements results in a new SCES, which might be more sustainable and more water-smart than the one envisaged at the starting line of the roadmapping process and therefore be the one to be implemented through the transfer actions described in the last step of the road map.

To define the boundaries for the SCES under study, identifying the specific networks around it – with the resources, technologies, actors, and governance regimes that exist in that particular case – constitutes the starting point of the exercise.

This stage identifies relevant actors, asset structures, today’s status, and the impact of existing drivers, pressures, and trends on the water management of the city/region as a reference point against which future developments will be addressed.

Scoping focuses on collecting information and gathering knowledge about becoming water smarter. This stage must ensure that all relevant parameters and information related to the objectives are available to the core team to draw a realistic picture of today's system.

At this step, some basic information has to be identified and collected through workshops and desktop study:

- Involved actors, stakeholders, institutions, and persons that are important for decision making
- Determination of the key objectives of the roadmap, its timeframe and perspective.
- General information about the geographical area, spatial boundaries, legal frameworks, and recent developments of the SCES
- Information and data about the elements of the SCES to be analysed to provide performance indicators and context information
- Identification of existing drivers, pressures and trends influencing the boundary conditions.

For the scoping phase is recommended the use of the governance assessment tool (GOCIWA) (WP4, D4.1, Damman *et al.*, 2021) as a point of departure. GOCIWA addresses the interplay between processes at different levels and scales. The roles and functioning of relevant actor networks, motivations, goals and ambitions, distribution of responsibilities and resources, and relevant policy instruments are considered. Special attention is paid to the interaction between institutional, ecological, and technological factors. Synergies and trade-offs between sector policies and between various stakeholder interests are also considered.

It aims to provide a simple aid for assessment and ultimately to facilitate wider uptake of water-smart solutions by identifying drivers, synergies and potential benefits and increasing the awareness of remaining challenges and their implications in specific settings.

GOCIWA supports the scoping phase by allowing to get an overview or making a "diagnosis" of the governance context, possible barriers, and potential for implementing circular water-smart solutions and developing industrial symbiosis based on reuse and/or resource extraction from water in a specific case or area.

Scoping consists of four working steps:

- S1: Identifying relevant actors
- S2: Objectives of the SCES
- S3: Elements of the SCES
- S4: Drivers, pressures, and trends towards a water-smart society

The working steps are described in the following sub-sections with direct reference to the GOCIWA tool (D4.1) (Damman *et al.*, 2021).

4.1.1 S1: Identifying relevant actors

In this working step, the core team has to identify the actors for the roadmap exercise. At this step, the phase of “Networks of action situations” of the GOCIWA tool (section 4.2 of D4.1) could be a useful instrument to be adopted.

Actors to be involved depending on what GOCIWA defines as *action situations*. Action situations refer to the main activities or interactions in the case considered, that lead to identifiable outputs. Wastewater treatment and sludge treatment will generally be included, as the compulsory core activities we want to transition towards more water-smart solutions. Water treatment may also be included (e.g., when the case involves calcite). Productization may involve different activities and should be specified for the given case (e.g., if it concerns producing treated water for irrigating food crops, or industry or household use, struvite or soil improvement products, biogas, bioenergy, biocomposites, etc.).

Action situations can be understood as spaces where actors make decisions and take actions, choosing among available options in light of information about the likely actions of others and the benefits and costs of potential outcomes.

Actors are the organizations and/or individuals that routinely extract and (re)use resource units (e.g., water, phosphorous, biochar) from the resource systems in each case. They include utilities, farmers, biogas plant operators, fertilizer and biocomposite producers, and their end-users.

Furthermore, the *Governance systems* have to be identified. They are considered the prevailing set of institutions through which the rules shaping the behaviour of the users are set and revised. In this initial step of the assessment, the scope is to identify which overarching governance systems or frameworks are brought into play in the specific case. These may be mainly the systems for managing water resources, environment, agriculture, and/or climate and energy, but also include waste management, urban planning, industry and/or building and construction (as in some of the WIDER UPTAKE demonstrations), and possibly others.

The relevant people from the actors and governance systems should participate actively in the working group and will support the work of the roadmap core team. It is proposed that the working group is organized as a Local CoP (see section 3.1). As described in D7.6 (Damman and Lund, 2021), CoP is an approach to establish and facilitate social learning and co-development towards a common objective.

After identifying the acting institutions' representatives, they must be informed about the roadmap exercise and listed in a contact management document by the roadmap core team. The list should provide additional information about the identified participants, as for instance describe if they are connected with other relevant sectors and stakeholders that could be involved in the process, or if they have a specific decision-making role.

Furthermore, it is important to mark in the list in which stage of the road mapping process the actors should be included; it is also possible that not all actors will participate in the whole road

mapping process (e.g., strategic decision makers might not have capacity to be involved in the more operational steps requiring groundwork such as data collection). Finally, please note that the actor’s management document is a living document in the roadmap work and will have a different composition for each case depending on the SCES.

Key aspects	S1: activities and support tools
Target	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identification of relevant actors • Establishing contact with the actors
Methods	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Initiation of establishing contacts (Template S1_1) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Identify relevant actors and governance systems ○ Get into first contact with relevant persons and institutions and check their interests, responsibilities, motivation, and availability • Motivate actors to participate in the roadmap work • Documentation of contact details in a contact management document (Template S1_2) • Kick-off-Workshop to launch the roadmap working group and explain the roadmap concept
Participants	<p>The roadmap working group consists of the roadmap core team plus the actors under the leadership of the roadmap manager.</p> <p>Roadmap manager has to organise a group of actors that will ideally provide high motivation for the roadmap application.</p> <p>The optimal group size (core team plus actors) should be around 8-10 persons. The core team and these actors form the roadmap working group.</p>
Data	None
Report	None
Output	Contact management document with a list of all relevant actors that includes their interests and responsibilities, as direct input to S2
Timeline	Start: asap; Duration: max. 1 month
Templates	<p>Template S1_1: Assessment chart – Context description (in chapter 5.1, D4.1 - Damman et al., 2021)</p> <p>Template S1_2: Actor management document</p>

4.1.2 S2: Objectives of the SCES

Given the boundaries of a chosen SCES to be realized, the working step S2 will define the specific objectives to be achieved by the SCES and how the achievement of these objectives should be measured.

WP5 has developed a set of common objectives for SCES to enable a utility, company, water sector planner or decision maker to measure how water-smart a process, a product or solution is, and how it contributes towards achieving the United Nation’s Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Starting from the proposed list, the work to be performed in S2 consists of verifying the objectives and describing how to measure their achievement in view of the following step S3 describing the system and the baseline performance versus the objectives. S2 will guide the collection of information for S3, and S2 and S3 are meant to run in parallel.

The output of S2 will be the list of objectives for the SCES and an overview of the criteria that will be used to measure the achievement of these. In addition, existing information, knowledge, and perspectives on the SCES and on transition needs will be collected by the roadmap core team.

The core team should conduct a desk study to assess the wider contexts, the structural context, and the specific context.

The analysis of the wider contexts entails collecting updated information on political, socio-economic, and cultural factors that may influence on the potential uptake of the water smart solution/s and realization of the SCES. The assessment chart provided in section 5.2 of D4.1 (Damman et al., 2021) can be used to support the analysis; also, the supporting excel file of the GOCIWA tool, Annex 3 of D4.1, has a separate sheet for assessing the wider context, which also contains examples of good sources for this work.

For the structural context and the specific context, the assessment charts provided in D4.1 in section 5.3 and 5.4 can be applied. These are also laid out in a separate sheet of D4.1 Annex 3. As alternative the core team can extrapolate the needed information via research, analysis of official reference documents like reports, statements, or existing studies.

For the structural and specific context, information can be gathered via individual interviews (one-to-one) with the actors identified as important participants/stakeholders in S1. To this aim, an interview guide that can provide information about the structural and case-specific contexts should be drafted. The interview guide should be used to get deeper knowledge on the particular contexts and should complement the desk studies conducted. It should therefore be developed and applied as a guide for semi-structured interviews not as a fixed and firm set of questions, but as a set of topics where the order, exact formulations and follow-up questions are tailored to the role and activities of the respective interviewees. Annex 2 of D4.1 provides an example of an interview guide, but the set of questions must be tailored to each case.

The core team can use the key question proposal (template S2_2, based on Annex 2 of D4.1) for structuring the interviews and assessing the relevant objectives and how to measure them. The goal is to identify existing adaptation plans (if applicable), the perspective and – if relevant – potential conflicts that are expected by each member of the roadmap group.

Key aspects	S2: activities and support tools
Target	Identify the specific objectives to be achieved by the SCES and how achievement of these should be assessed.

Methods	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Desk study • Use of the GOCIWA assessment charts and supporting excel file (Damman et al., 2021) • List of objectives and criteria proposed in D5.1, chapter 6 (Nessler Seglem K and Helness, 2023) • One-to-one interviews with actors from S1 (and others if needed) and • A Workshop in S4 held by the core team
Participants	Roadmap working group (external participants will be individually interviewed by a core team member)
Data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the qualitative data produced through the interviews • the selected objective and assessment criteria
Report	SCES map that illustrates the analysed SCES, their objectives, the criteria
Output	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A quick overview of the SCES, its motivation, the objectives, how to assess them and potential conflicts between different interests • Direct input to S3, F1, F2, B2 and TR1
Timeline	Start: month 1; Duration: 2 to 3 months
Templates	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Template S2 1: SCES map • Template S2 2: Semi-structured interviews, D4.1, ANNEX 2 (Damman et al., 2021) • Template S2 3: List of objectives and criteria based on the WIDER UPTAKE WS&S assessment framework, D5.1, chapter 6 (Nessler Seglem K and Helness, 2023) • Template S2 4: Assessment charts and excel file of GOCIWA tool, section 5.2, 5.3 and 5.4 of D4.1 (Damman et al., 2021) and related supporting spreadsheets in the GOCIWA tool, Annex 3 of D4.

4.1.3 S3: Elements of the SCES

In the third working step of Scoping, the system will be described by selected indicators and context information.

The data collection itself incorporates the WS&S assessment framework of WIDER UPTAKE in WP5 (version for testing in D5.1, M36) with its five dimensions: social, economic, environmental, governance and technical performance. The number of performance indicators used for each dimension and its assessment is not finalized at the time of writing. Still, when available it will be linked to the road mapping exercise as supporting tool (in D6.7). The current version is provided in D5.1, chapter 6 and accompanying excel file (Nessler Seglem K and Helness, 2023).

Furthermore, the data collection should inform:

- if plans exist or not that can favour the achievement of the objectives;
- the territorial limit (boundary) of the road mapping process involving the existing plants;
- the list of the legal framework to refer to;
- recent development related to the system (e.g., upgrading, or new project). These inputs are defined as context information.

The data collection process can support the roadmap work significantly, because the existing SCES can be described and visualized by qualitative and quantitative characteristics at an early stage. According to the overview of objectives (as an output from S2) the data collection in S3 should be focussed on these objectives and should leave out irrelevant ones. The data collection will set the basis for the progress in the next stages (e.g., by performing a baseline assessment), and particularly in the Forecasting and Backcasting stages.

To organise the quantitative data collection in S3, this guideline will build on the WS&S assessment framework datasheet developed in WP5 (D5.1, Nessler Seglem and Helness, 2023) (proposed as Template S3_2 and to be implemented in the guide in D6.7). The data sheet links the dimensions to objectives, assessment criteria and corresponding indicators. If needed the performance indicators can be modified or added. Guidelines for local adaptation and application of the WS&S assessment framework is provided in D5.2 (Nessler Seglem K and Helness, 2023) under development at the time of writing. The instructions provided in D5.2 will be of valuable support and be described in D6.7 for step S3.

Furthermore, as envisaged in WP5, the data collection goes in line with other data collections in WIDER UPTAKE, and the assessment methods and tools provided in WP2 and WP3, i.e., D2.1 Procedure for monitoring and control of health and quality risks (Ardiyanti R, et al., 2021) and D3.1 Framework for Circularity and Efficiency Assessment and Optimisation of Symbiotic Circular Economy Solutions (Bhambhani A, et al., 2022) can be used to provide more detailed analysis and quantification of some indicators in the WS&S assessment framework.

If agreements on confidentiality of the data and the data analysis is required, a possible template for “Confidentiality Agreement and Code of Conduct” based on Hein et al. (2010) is provided (template S3_1).

Key aspects	S3: activities and support tools
Target	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide information about the elements of the SCES in view of meeting the water-smartness objectives, set in S2. • Perform the assessment of the actual SCES by using the WS&S assessment framework for the starting time (e.g., baseline assessment)
Methods	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Comply with rules of confidentiality, if needed (template S3_1) • Data collection by the actors using the WS&S assessment framework (template S3_2) and the template for context information (template S3_3)

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Support during data collection will be provided by roadmap core team • Guidelines for local adaptation and application of the WS&S assessment framework is provided also in D5.2 (Nessler Seglem K and Helness, 2023)
Participants	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Actors identified in S1 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ provide data and information and fill out the template S3_2. • Roadmap core team <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ provides support to fill out the template S3_2 ○ explains data classifications and definitions ○ provides results of the data collection via reports
Data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data variables and context information, documented in the template S3_2 • The WS&S framework (WP5) organises performance indicators and provides illustrations for the report
Report	The system profile including qualitative and quantitative water-smartness aspects
Output	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overview of the elements of the system, action fields and relevant context information • Direct input to S4 and F1, F2
Timeline	Start: month 1; Duration: max. 3 months
Templates	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Template S3_1: Confidentiality Agreement and Code of Conduct • Template S3_2: <i>WS&S assessment framework, based on D5.1 (Nessler Seglem K and Helness, 2023)</i> • Template S3_3: Context information

4.1.4 S4: Drivers, pressures, and trends towards a water smart society

The last working step of Scoping (S4) analyses existing drivers, pressures and trends that affect the achievement of the SCES objectives and the water management of the city/region in which the SCES is realized. A key element of S4 is a Scoping-Workshop with all members of the roadmap working group. The Scoping-Workshop can be organised as a joint workshop with the Forecasting-Workshop 1 (Figure 2). The goal of this workshop is a common understanding of the existing drivers, pressures, and trends to the SCES realization, adjustments and / or alternatives. This workshop finalises the stage of Scoping and summarizes the actual challenges and development opportunities that have to be taken into account for the forecasting stage. The summary can be simply presented as in template S4_1.

The Scoping-Workshop should be organised by the roadmap core team. The workshop content will be very dependent on the results of the preceding working steps.

Also, if the GOCIWA assessment charts for the structural context and the specific context have been used in step S2, relevant inputs for S4 might be included and further discussed during the workshop.

Key aspects	S4: activities and support tools
Target	Analyse drivers, pressures and trends affecting the objectives
Methods	Scoping-/Forecasting-workshop: organise a workshop involving the roadmap working group
Participants	Roadmap working group (core team plus actors; external experts if needed)
Data	Qualitative and quantitative information on relevant drivers, trends, and pressures
Report	Short drivers, pressures, and trends report
Output	Direct input to F1, F2, B2 and TR1.
Timeline	Start: end of month 3; Duration: a workshop format
Templates	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Template S3 2: <i>WS&S assessment framework, based on D5.1 (Nessler Seglem K and Helness, 2023)</i> • Template S4 1: <i>Driver, Pressure and Trends overview resulting from S4 (based on D6.3, to be revised in D6.7)</i>

4.2 FORECASTING: Envisioning the system in a future world

Forecasting comprises the following three aspects:

- F1: Projecting possible futures (or scenarios)
- F2: Envisioning the SCES in the future
- F3: Synthesising

It thus comprises both a projection of the possible future of the external system and a vision of the desired state of the system in the sphere of influence of the user (i.e., the actors of the SCES). A synthesis will test the compatibility of both and identify possible conflicts and needs for adaptive remedial action to be considered in designing the Transfer step.

The rationale of forecasting is to extrapolate current trends into the future, anticipate new future trends and obtain a prospective view. The parameters to be forecasted will largely follow the elements of S3 of the scoping stage but should also anticipate factors not considered today.

From a methodological point of view, several methods, both quantitative and qualitative, can be used to perform this task, including (amongst others) time-series methods, interviews with experts, etc. The choice of the optimal method depends on each case and the data availability and its degree of detail. Still, it is common to use a mix of different techniques.

4.2.1 F1: Projecting possible futures (or scenarios)

The specific task of this working step will be to project future changes in boundary conditions of the SCES and to forecast what the future will look like, e.g., in 30 years from now outside the water sector.

This activity can again be supported by the GOCIWA tool for assessing the wider, structural, and specific contexts (see for illustration purposes the example of assessment chart for the wider context, Figure 7, extracted from D4.1, which will be adapted in D6.7). Direct inputs to F1 will be provided by D6.4, which will describe common features in the scenarios used for the testing of the methods and tools developed in WP2, WP3, WP4 and WP5 and provide a set of future scenarios and guidance on how to define scenarios that will be included for further use in the roadmap guide (D6.7).

Predictions for a variety of factors may extrapolate from past trends drawing on time series and statistics. However, where no such sound data base is available, the projections can be based on assumptions, derived from literature, expert interviews or the like. Practically, these ideas will be developed in the Scoping-Workshop (S4) which can be organised as a dual-purpose event to collect data on past and current trends and describe their future progression.

As exemplified in [template F1 1](#), based on D4.1, a semi-quantitative description of current and future trends could be documented for the various factors, based on the proposed questions. Additionally, the analysis should provide a first indication of which system’s elements might be impacted. A more detailed causal relationship between pressures and impacts can be elaborated in a subsequent step, F2 (this may include quantitative estimates of specific key indicators for the time horizon set for the road mapping exercise, as already used in S3 for the starting time (e.g., baseline assessment), see F2). The range of factors to be considered depends on the past experience of the participants. Still, it should be complemented by information from a wider area (e.g., state of the environment reports, regional climate change scenarios, etc.). Finally, **the different future trends can be clustered into scenarios.**

As this step is to analyse future expected changes in the external system, which is by definition not under the sphere of influence of the water utilities, it may require a different set of experts and actors to be involved.

As described above, F1 will further benefit from the instructions provided in D6.4 and therefore be extended accordingly in D6.7.

Key aspects	F1: activities and support tools
Target	Description of the possible future environment(s)
Methods	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Description and future projection of trends by time-series analysis of data (joint workshop with S4, Scoping-/Forecasting-Workshop) • Calculate or estimate impacts on operation, derive future Performance Indicators

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Down-scaling and transfer of national or regional scenarios • Own scenario building
Participants	Roadmap working group
Data	Quantification of a range of projected futures, isolate major trends (low, medium, high scenarios)
Report	Report with relevant environments and expected implications
Output	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Portfolio of context scenarios • Set of updated comparison with S3 components inventory, major state differences, updated summary flow sheet / matrix • Basis for identification of options or transfer action fields (T), Input to F3
Timeline	Start: month 5; Duration: 2-3 months
Templates	<i>Template F1_1: Examples of factors to be assessed in projecting different futures (copied from the GOCIWA tool, D4.1 (Damman et al., 2021), for illustration purposes, to be customized or adapted and included in D6.7 based on D6.4)</i>

4.2.2 F2: Envisioning the SCES in the future

Envisioning will define the future desired state of the SCES, which could be an alternative SCES from the one of interest due to projected possible futures. It has to be seen in the larger context of societal and political aspirations and thus involve stakeholders from these fields as well. It will be beneficial to involve customers and the more general public and to establish a consultation process to arrive at an agreed vision.

The governing idea is to describe the future SCES in terms of service and sustainability, having regard to the circumstances, restrictions and boundary conditions of the specific region as identified in F1. Consequently, the approach should develop realistic but still ambitious expectations based on the knowledge of the current status of the infrastructure, the service expectations of the users, relevant trends and pressures, the financial abilities of the region etc. If sufficient time is available, this can be supported by customer and stakeholder consultations to investigate their preferences, expectations, and acceptance.

Drawing on the current SCES profile and identified pressures and challenges, envisioning will define how the SCES will look in the set time horizon and formulate the agreed ambition. The vision shall describe the desired future state of the considered system in a qualitative and, if possible, quantitative way. To this end, the roadmap working group and defined participants can update the indicators selected from the current state (S3) to the future desired performance. This can take a qualitative or semi-quantitative description such as “increase” or “reduction”, “more”, “less”, “better”, etc. For quantitative results, the application of Template S3_2 from Scoping is recommended for Envisioning, too.

The vision statement should:

- Express the commitment to improvement,
- Summarise targets for performance (indicators).

Key aspects	F2: activities and support tools
Target	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Picture the future desired state of the system • Identify preferences and ambitions • Open trajectories for transition • Anticipate countermeasures to identified trends (F1)
Methods	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Envisioning and projecting exercise in an expert workshop • Envisioning-Workshop or survey to elucidate customer and stakeholder expectations of water services • Data collection by the actors using the water-smartness assessment framework (template S3_2) • Guidelines for local adaptation and application of the WS&S assessment framework provided in D5.2 (Nessler Seglem K and Helness, 2023)
Participants	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Roadmap working group • From outside the utility: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ NGOs, e.g., consumer protection organisation, ○ Politicians
Data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Qualitative information about the actors' expectations of a desired future state • Defined ambition for operational performance (selected Performance Indicators) • Possibly quantify a range of underlying parameters such as future demand patterns, resource pattern, demand reduction targets, etc. • The WS&S assessment framework (WP5) organises performance indicators and provides illustrations for the report
Report	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vision Statement / Declaration of development objectives • Updated Template S3_2 from S3
Output	To F3
Timeline	Start: month 6; Duration: 2- 5 months
Templates	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Template S3_2: WS&S assessment framework, based on D5.1 (Nessler Seglem K and Helness, 2023)

4.2.3 F3: Synthesis

In the synthesis step, the information generated in F1 and F2 will be processed to create a consolidated vision with prioritised ambitions. Furthermore, this step analyses the probable

impact the anticipated (external) changes may have on the system, as they exist and operate today. As a result, the compatibility of the vision and the diagnosed major trends in the environment shall be ensured. This will be done by the roadmap core team and be presented to the public in a hearing.

Key aspects	F3: activities and support tools
Target	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Define, and visualise gaps between projected changes and future vision, compliance Identify areas of priority action and core competence
Methods	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Internal evaluation round Public consultation, hearing
Participants	Roadmap core team, public, end-users, NGO or only roadmap working group
Data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> None
Report	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ambition report with prioritised elements of a vision
Output	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Input to Backcasting stage Descriptive characterisation of future services and how they will be delivered
Timeline	Start: month 8; Duration: 2 months
Templates	None

4.3 BACKCASTING: Projecting possible visions back into the present

In the roadmap, the Backcasting stage builds directly from the Forecasting stage, using the outputs from steps F2 and F3 as a starting point. The overall purpose of this stage is to characterise how a SCES might shift from its present state to the desired end point to better achieve the set objectives. This stage therefore consists of two basic working steps:

- B1: defining intermediate state(s) state between the present situation and the (future) vision.
- B2: identifying measures to facilitate transitions from state to state

4.3.1 B1: Defining intermediate state(s)

The purpose of this working step is to identify and describe at least one intermediate state between the present situation and the (future) vision. For the roadmap, one of these intermediate states is centred on a year or a time period. Whether or not additional intermediate states are deemed necessary/useful can be left to the discretion of the roadmap core team.

Each intermediate state should be described both with qualitative and quantitative information. The data/ performance indicators used here should be consistent with those used

in the Scoping and Forecasting stages. For describing the intermediate states, the template S3_2 can be used by feeding forecasted or predicted/assumed data.

Key aspects	B1: activities and support tools
Target	Identification and description of the agreed intermediate state(s) within the start and end point of the set time horizon
Methods	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Initial description of intermediate states using qualitative information, data/performance indicators of the template S3_2 that are consistent with the future scenarios identified in the Forecasting stage. • Guidelines for local adaptation and application of the WS&S assessment framework provided in D5.2 (Nessler Seglem K and Helness, 2023) • Elicitation of feedback from a wider range of actors, to develop consensus around intermediate state descriptions.
Participants	Ideally, the actors should be the same as those who participated in the Forecasting stage
Data	Similar to S3, F1, F2
Report	Qualitative and / or quantitative descriptions of the intermediate state(s)
Output	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • See above “Report” • Direct input to B2 and Transfer stage
Timeline	Start: month 10; Duration: 2 months
Templates	Template S3_2 : WS&S assessment framework, based on D5.1 (Nessler Seglem K and Helness, 2023)

4.3.2 B2: Identifying measures to facilitate transitions from state to state

The purpose of this working step is to identify transition measures that will allow the SCES to shift from its present state towards the intermediate state and the vision (of the SCES). To that end, the step could be split into two phases:

- B2a – The identification of short/medium-term measures to achieve the intermediate state(s) described in B1.
- B2b – The identification of longer-term measures to move from the intermediate state(s) to the end point state identified in the Forecasting stage.

To complete this step, it is advisable to refer back to the description prepared in S3. Ideally, transition measures should be identified for each of the elements of the SCES that are relevant from the perspective of the SCES for transitioning to the envisioned one.

Furthermore, each transition measure should be accompanied by a brief description of its necessity and viability, including a general assessment of:

- How it will help achieve the desired state
- Its relative importance in achieving the desired state
- Who is responsible for its delivery
- Estimated timeframe for its delivery
- How much investment is needed (rough estimate)
- What are the prospects and risks
- Socio-political factors that may facilitate and/or hinder its implementation

The roadmap core team should have primary responsibility for developing an initial (limited) set of measures as a starting point and then obtaining additional input from the roadmap working group. However, the primary mechanism for obtaining that input will be the Transitioning-Workshop (see Figure 2) – with one session in the workshop devoted to the short/medium-term measures (B2a) and one devoted to the longer-term measures (B2b).

On the other hand, the Roadmap-Workshop could be used to get the results of B2. To help actors be prepared for the workshop, the core team can distribute the initial set of transition measures for consideration. Transition measures can address technological developments, but also non-technological actions (e.g., new business models, citizens awareness, policies innovation, etc.) that need to be performed to realize the intermediate and long terms states of the SCES. During the workshop, actors could discuss the merits of the measures and potentially propose additional ones. After the workshop, the core team could then summarize the outcomes in an outline document.

Key aspects	B2: activities and support tools
Target	Identification and description of transition measures
Methods	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Circulate an initial set of measures (both short/medium-term and longer-term) • Optional: organize the Transitioning- Workshop • Utilise the Roadmap Workshop to discuss the proposed measures and obtain feedback from the working group
Participants	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The roadmap core team sets out the initial measures • The actors should be invited to participate in the relevant sessions of the Roadmap Workshop
Data	None
Report	Outline document describing agreed measures (both short/medium term and longer-term)
Output	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Outline document (see above) • Direct input to Transfer stage
Timeline	Start: month 11; Duration: 2 months (general application)
Templates	Template S3 2 : water-smartness assessment framework, based on D5.1 (Nessler Seglem K and Helness, 2023)

4.4 TRANSFER: Creating the roadmap

The last stage of the road-mapping process is to evaluate the results of the analysis and transfer them into a roadmap. This includes providing some chronological information on activities undertaken and results. Creating a roadmap means documenting and transferring identified action fields and measures (defined through workshops) into prioritized recommendations for responsible people and institutions. An adaptive roadmap normally includes listings of relevant action fields and identified measures, indications of prioritisation, time scales and milestones, progress monitoring aspects and an illustration of possible or expected prospects and risks.

To organise the transfer of this knowledge into the roadmap effectively, the relevant topics and measures of the system as identified in the preceding step B2 should first be summarised in transfer action fields, and then secondly be evaluated to create the roadmap.

The result of the Transfer stage is the roadmap itself.

Transfer consists of two working steps:

- TR1: Evaluating transfer action fields and their measures
- TR2: Creating the roadmap

4.4.1 TR1: Evaluating transfer action fields and their measures

The purpose of this working step is to evaluate the transfer action fields. Therefore, the measures as defined in Backcasting step B2 should be organized/listed according to this aim (e.g., by a systematic numbering or similar) in a prioritised action plan. Categories of prioritization are strongly dependent on the action fields and local conditions and should be defined in collaboration with the members of the working group.

Furthermore, TR1 should analyse possible interactions between action fields, the chronological sequence with milestones, progress monitoring, responsibilities, risks and prospects and barriers for the implementation of measures and a range of (roughly estimated) costs. Template TR1_1 shows an example of how the output from TR1 can be systemised. The format and design of the prioritised action plan will be defined within the project by the core team. Transfer action fields should be listed with their short-term and long-term measures and other relevant information. The output of this working step deal with as preparation for the last Roadmap-Workshop in TR2.

Key aspects	TR1: activities and support tools
Target	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Evaluating the transfer action fields and their measures • Define a prioritisation scheme • Analyse interactions between action fields, the chronological sequence of measures, and their risks, barriers, and prospects

Methods	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use the output from B2 (measures and all available information) • Collection of data from previous stages, chronological information for activities, first recommendations for milestones and categorization for prioritization of TA
Participants	Roadmap working group (core team plus actors)
Data	Results from Scoping, Forecasting, Backcasting
Report	Overview of transfer action fields with their measures and level of priority
Output	Direct input to TR2.
Timeline	Start: month 14; Duration: 2-3 months
Templates	Template TR1_1 : prioritised action plan

4.4.2 TR2: Creating the roadmap

The purpose of this working step is to transfer the results from TR1 and the other working steps into a final reporting document called a roadmap. Therefore, the result of TR2 is the roadmap itself. A template of a possible table of content is provided (template TR2_1) and can be adapted on need.

Key aspects	TR2: activities and support tools
Target	Create the roadmap
Methods	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Roadmap-Workshop: organisation of an external workshop involving external participants from relevant actors of the pilot city • Graphical representation and writing the roadmap • Review of the final roadmap document
Participants	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Roadmap working group (core team plus external participants) • Establish an editorial team for graphical representation and writing
Data	Results TR1, Scoping, Forecasting, Backcasting
Report	Roadmap
Output	Roadmap
Timeline	Start: month 16; Duration: 2 months
Templates	Template TR2_1 : Basic structure of the Roadmap

5 Conclusions

Deliverable 6.6 (D6.6) is the first version of the WIDER UPTAKE roadmap guide, a manual to organise transition planning for wider uptake of water-smart solutions through the realization of symbiotic circular economy solutions (SCES).

The users of the guide are managers and decision makers providing water services and related solutions in the water sector.

The roadmap structure is divided into four main steps: scoping, forecasting, backcasting, and transfer. The four main stages are structured into different numbers of working steps. Each road mapping step and working step are enriched with detailed explanations and point at supporting templates based on material and tools developed, or under development, in other work packages (WP) of WIDER UPTAKE.

D6.6 is considered a mock-up of the final version, D6.7, where the preliminary identified outcomes from other WPs are referred to as valuable supporting tools for creating the roadmap. Along with the further development and testing of those outcomes and the identification of new ones the supporting templates will be fully integrated in the final version of the guide.

The guide is grounded on the roadmap methodology described by the project TRUST (Hein *et al.*, 2010) and reflects the same classical steps of the road mapping process.

The advancement of the state of the art with respect to TRUST has been the adaptation of the approach to the domain of WIDER UPTAKE and the proposed integration with specific assessment tools developed in this project. Among the outcomes of the project, the following approaches stand out in this first mapping exercise as valuable tools proposed to assist the road mapping exercise:

- The GOCIWA tool, by WP4, whose assessment charts and templates can be adopted to perform the working steps S1-S2 and F1.
- The water-smartness and sustainability (WS&S) assessment approach of WIDER UPTAKE (by WP5), with its five dimensions: social, economic, environmental, governance and technical performance, proposed to support the working steps: S2-S4, F2, B1-B2.
- The assessment methods and tools provided in WP2 for monitoring and control of health and quality risks and in WP3 for circularity and efficiency assessment and optimisation of SCES, which can provide more detailed analysis and quantification of some indicators in the WS&S assessment framework (WP5) when this is used in S3 and other working steps.
- The Local Community of Practice (CoP), by WP7, whose establishment, performed according to the guidance provided by WP7, can be the arena of key actors and stakeholders appointed as roadmap working group, i.e., responsible for the creation of the roadmap.

The roadmap guide described in this deliverable will be further elaborated to encapsulate the supporting tools delivered by other WPs (also extending the list of templates identified so far,

if the case), and will be validated by selected case studies of the project to comment on the practicability and feasibility of the concept. After being tested, the feedback will help to improve the clarity of the document and its templates as well as provide insights on how to facilitate its usability as inputs to the final version D6.7.

Furthermore, the final version of the guide, D6.7, will incorporate information specific to the context of developing water-smart and sustainable SCES, i.e., objectives and criteria, indicators, drivers, pressures, trends, required for the scoping step, based on the validated framework of WP5 and the discussion presented in D6.3, and future scenarios, based on the common features in the scenarios used for the testing of the methods and tools developed in WP2, WP3, WP4 and WP5 and outlined in D6.4. The idea is to inspire future users by providing input for elaborating their roadmaps based on the information gained from the WIDER UPTAKE case studies.

6 References

Akon-Yamga G., Cosenza A., Damman S., Di Trapani D, Helness H., Jovanovic O., Kapelan Z., Mäkitie T., Mannina G., Pollert J., Strogonov V., Ugarelli R., Wanner J., Østerhus S.W., 2023. Roadmap database. [D6.3](#), WIDER UPTAKE Project.

Rizza Ardiyanti R., Hallé C., Azrague K., 2021. Procedure for monitoring and control of health and quality risks. [D2.1](#), WIDER UPTAKE Project.

Bhambhani A., van der Hoek J. P., Kapelan Z., Werner A., 2022. Framework for Circularity and Efficiency Assessment and Optimisation of Symbiotic Solutions. [D3.1](#), WIDER UPTAKE Project.

Damman S., Brynthe Lund H., Mäkitie T., 2021. Governance assessment for Circular Economy based on Water resources (GOCIWA). [D4.1](#), WIDER UPTAKE Project.

Damman S., Brynthe Lund H., 2021. First report on Communities of Practice. [D7.6](#), WIDER UPTAKE Project

Hein, A., Neskovic, M., Hochstrat, R., Smith, H. (2010). Roadmap guideline: A manual to organise transition planning in Urban Water Cycle Systems. D13.1, TRUST project.

Nessler Seglem K., Helness H., 2023. Framework for holistic assessment of water smartness and progress towards SDGs. [D5.1](#), WIDER UPTAKE project.

Nessler Seglem K., Helness H., 2023. Guidelines for local adaptation and application of the water smartness and sustainability framework in a given case. [D5.2](#), WIDER UPTAKE project.

Water Europe (2017). The value of water. Water Europe Water Vision 2030, Water Europe, Brussels. ISBN: 9789028362130. <https://watereurope.eu/> (accessed the 15th of December 2022).

Annex 1: Templates for the Scoping step

A1.1 – Template S1_1: Assessment chart – Context description

Case definition		Action situation 1*	Action situation 2*	Action situation 3*	Action situation 4*
Dimension	Questions	Wastewater treatment	Sludge treatment	Productization	Use
Resources	What resource systems are implicated in the studied case of industrial symbiosis / water-smart solutions?				
	What resource units are involved in the chain of activities considered?				
Focal interactions	What are the main activities and decision points?				
	What are the focal solutions, technologies?				
	What are the desired outcomes (products, ecosystem services)?				
Actors	What categories of actors are involved?				
Governance systems	What sectors and governance systems are implicated?				
<p>* Action situations refer to the main activities or interactions in the case considered, that lead to identifiable outputs. Wastewater treatment and sludge treatment will generally be included, as the compulsory core activities we want to transition towards more circularity. In some cases, water treatment may also be included (e.g. when the case involves calcite). Productization may involve different activities and should be specified for the given case (e.g. if it concerns producing treated water for irrigating food crops, or industry or household use, struvite or soil improvement products, biogas, bioenergy, biocomposites, etc.). The same goes for use, which refers to the use of the products considered in each case.</p>					

Figure 7: Assessment chart – context definition – GOCIWA tool (Damman et al., 2021) – Road map proposed template S1_1 to be further developed in D6.7

A1.2 – Template S1_2: Actor management document

Table 2: Actor management document – adapted from TRUST - Road map proposed template S1_2

Governance system	Actors	Name and contact data of person/representative	Mediator/bridges (yes/no); type of mediator	Problem-solving decision capacity/decision competence	Roadmap involvement: Scoping, Forecasting, Backcasting, Transfer	Task description in road mapping.

A1.3 – Template S2_1: SCES map template

Table 3: SCES map template – data supporting S2; VC = Value Chain (Template S2_1)

To be designed in D6.7 to support summarizing the information gained in S2 via desk study and interviews

S2							Obj: social dimension			Obj: Environment
Type	Motivation	VC: Water reuse	VC: Nutrient recovery	VC: Compost production	VC: Manufacturing of products	VC: Energy recovery	S1	S2	S3	...
<i>Insert type of SCES e.g., water reuse, energy production...</i>	<i>Insert here the motivation to implement the SCES e.g., cost and energy optimization, regulation, ...</i>	<i>Insert yes or no</i>	<i>Insert yes or no</i>	<i>Explain the relevance for the SCES, add information on assessment criteria</i>	<i>Explain the relevance for the SCES, add information on assessment criteria</i>	<i>Explain the relevance for the SCES, add information on assessment criteria</i>	<i>Explain the relevance for the SCES, add information on assessment criteria</i>			

A1.4 – Template S2_2: Semi-structured interviews

To be adapted in D6.7 based on D4.1, ANNEX 2 (Damman et al., 2021)

A1.5 – Template S2_3: List of objectives and criteria based on the WIDER UPTAKE water-smartness assessment framework

To be developed in D6.7 based on validated version of the WIDER UPTAKE water-smartness and sustainability (WS&S) assessment framework (WP5, D5.1, chapter 6) (Template S2_3)

The current list of objectives only is presented for illustration purposes.

Table 4: List of objectives from the WIDER UPTAKE water-smartness and sustainability (WS&S) assessment framework (WP5, D5.1, chapter 6) (Template S2_3)

Dimension	Objectives
Social	S1 Maintain the social benefits provided by traditional water- and/or wastewater utilities S2 Provide human well-being by the recovered resources and final products of the SCES S3 Enhance knowledge and acceptance of the SCES, its recovered resources and final products
Environment	En1 Minimize negative environmental impacts En2 Preserve nature En3 Have positive climate effect
Economic	Ec1 Maximise the economic value added in/by/through the SCES value chain Ec2 Give added economic benefits to the parties of the SCES Ec3 Give added economic benefits to society
Governance	G1 Comply with regulations, rules, and guidelines G2 Contribute towards Integrated Water Management G3 Have participatory governance
Technical Performance	TP1 Achieve targets for traditional services provided by water- and/or wastewater utilities TP2 Deliver correct quality and quantity of the recovered resources and final products of the SCES TP3 Minimize waste and keep resources in use

A1.6 – Template S2_4: Assessment charts and excel file of GOCIWA tool

To be developed in D6.7 based on the assessment charts in section 5.2, 5.3 and 5.4 of D4.1 (Damman et al., 2021) and related supporting spreadsheets in the GOCIWA tool, Annex 3 of D4.

A1.7 – Template S3_1: Confidentiality Agreement and Code of Conduct

This code of conduct is adapted from the Code of Conduct proposed by the TRUST project (Hein et al., 2010). Adherence to this code will contribute to an efficient, effective, and innovative roadmap exercise.

This code of conduct is developed to

- guide roadmap efforts
- advance the professionalism and effectiveness of roadmaps' creation
- help protect its members from harm.

Principle of Confidentiality

- Treat roadmap findings as confidential to the individuals and organisations involved. Such information must not be communicated to third parties without the prior consent of the partner who shared the information.
- When seeking prior consent, make sure that you specify clearly what information is to be shared and with whom.
- Neither the roadmap team nor the utility may distribute results of the roadmap work without the permission of the participating companies. The (in the following: “roadmap team”) [Insert the name of all institution that belong to the roadmap core team. (Please, delete these comments after filling in)] will treat all information and data given by the (in the following “actor”) [Insert the name of the participating actor for the roadmap procedure (Please, (delete these comments after filling in))] as strictly confidential, unless they are already in the public domain.

Adjustments to this non-disclosure agreement may be decided by the members of the roadmap working group

Principle of co-operation and communication

- Demonstrate commitment to engagement with the roadmap procedure by being prepared prior to participating in the roadmap working group.
- Help your roadmap partners by providing them information needed for the roadmap work in a co-operative and transparent way. Communicate fully and early in the relationship to clarify expectations, avoid misunderstanding and establish mutual interest in the roadmap exchange.
- Respect the corporate culture of partner organisations and work within mutually agreed procedures.
- Publications are to be agreed with all members of the roadmap working group.

Principle of Legality

- Take legal advice (if needed) before participating in the roadmap working group and before providing information or data.
- Avoid discussions or actions that could lead to or imply an interest in restraint of trade, market and/or customer allocation schemes, price fixing, dealing arrangements, bid rigging or bribery. Neglect any activity in terms of dispersion of information by any means that could be interpreted as improper, including the breach, or inducement of a breach, of any duty to maintain confidentiality.

Any participating company/institution ensures the content of the non-disclosure agreement at the start of the roadmap procedure.

Place, Date

Authorized signatory of the participating organization

Actors stamp

A1.8 – Template S3_2: WS&S assessment framework

The water-smartness and sustainability (WS&S) assessment framework (D5.1, Nessler Seglem and Helness, 2023) will be embedded as excel file in D6.7 and supported by guidelines for its adopting based on the guidelines provided in D5.2 (Nessler Seglem and Helness, 2023).

A1.9 – Template S3_3: Context information

Table 5: Context information to be gathered during step S3 (template S3_3)

S3			
Element of the system			
Existing plans	Boundary	Legal framework	Recent development
<i>Insert yes or no</i>	<i>Insert here the limit of the boundary and areas</i>	<i>List the legal framework to refer to</i>	<i>Insert here if the plants have been subjected to upgrading or other</i>

A1.10 – Template S4_1: Drivers, Pressure and Trends overview resulting from S4

Table 6 is based on the database provided in D6.3, however, it should be revised in D6.7 to align with terminology used across the project, e.g., the dimensions proposed for Drivers, Pressure and Trends could be aligned with the five dimensions (Social, Environment, Economic, Governance and Technical Performance) adopted in WP5.

Table 6: Drivers, Pressure and Trends overview resulting from S4 (Template S4_1)

S4									
Drivers				Pressures				Trends	
Social	Regulatory	Environment	Market	Social	Regulatory	Environment	Market	Observed trends	Future trends or development
<i>Explain</i>	<i>E.g., increasing energy consumption, increasing level of water smart...</i>	<i>E.g., the current level will increase thanks to investments or vice versa</i>							

Annex 2: Templates for the Forecasting step

A2.1 – Template F1_1: Examples of factors to be assessed in projecting different futures - Wider context assessment chart (D4.1)

Examples of factors to be assessed in projecting different futures (copied from the GOCIWA tool, D4.1, for illustration purpose, to be customized or adapted and included in D6.7 based on D6.4)

Table 7: Wider context assessment chart (D4.1) – here proposed as Template F1_1 – adjustments will be provided in D6.7 based on D6.4

Wider contexts	
Demography	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What is the projected national population growth? • What is the urbanisation rate, according to national statistics?
Environmental context	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What are the anticipated impacts of climate change on precipitation and water resources? • What are the main pressures on the water resources in the country? • To what extent is physical water scarcity a challenge? • To what extent is water quality a challenge? • What is the total discharge from wastewater in the country? • What are the implications of the identified pressures, for water cycle services? • To what extent is resource scarcity a recognised problem? • What are the prevailing climate targets and their relevance for uptake of water-smart solutions?
Political context	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How is the country rated, in terms of peace and stability? • What is the perceived level of corruption? • To what extent are citizens involved in public decision-making? • To what extent are the SDGs implemented in national frameworks, and how does the country perform in terms of the SDGs? • To what extent does the country engage in international cooperation on sustainable water management and CE?

wider uptake

Economic context	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What is the level of GDP per capita and GDP growth? • What is the unemployment rate? • How does the country score on the Human Development Index? • What are the largest industrial sectors, in terms of GDP and employment? • What is the reported degree of circularity (as per circularity gap reporting)? • What is the size of informal sector? • Are there regional differences (e.g., in terms of economic development and enterprise) influencing the potential for water-smart solutions? • How is the distributed access and level of service for clean water and sanitation?
Socio-cultural context	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What is the number and distribution of different language/ethnic groups? • What is the level of environmental awareness in the national population? • How is the public access to environmental information? • To what extent are there active pro-environmental NGOs, and what is their capacity? • What are the popular perceptions and attitudes concerning use and reuse of water resources (as noted in research or expressed in public media)?

Annex 3: Templates for the Backcasting step

The templates for B1 and B2 is the [Template S3_2](#): water-smartness and sustainability (WS&S) assessment framework

Annex 4: Templates for the Transfer step

A4.1 – Template TR1_1: Examples of transfer action fields: prioritised action plan

Table 8: Examples of transfer action (TA) fields: prioritised action plan (Template TR1_1)

TA and priority	Measures till (e.g.) 2026	Measures till (e.g.) 2030	Responsible Actors	Range of cost	Interaction with other TA	Limitations and barriers

A4.2 – Template TR2_1: Basic structure of the roadmap

The proposed template will be enriched in D6.7 with hyperlinks addressing the templates to be used.

Template_TR2_1: Basic structure of the roadmap

1. Scoping the today's SCES
 - a. Actors management document
 - b. SCES elements and objectives
 - c. Relevant drivers, pressures, and trends (Results of the Scoping-Workshop)
2. Envisioning the future SCES
 - a. Vision
 - b. Separate sectors and their vision / objectives (Results of the Envisioning-Workshop in the Forecasting phase)
3. Develop the measures with Backcasting
 - a. Measures and transfer action fields
 - b. Prioritisation of transfer action fields separately
4. Illustration and summary
 - a. Visualize the roadmap
5. Conclusions
6. Appendix